

Recommended citation: Molnár, G., Szuts, Z., & Orosz, B. (2019). From drawings to digital devices - Additives to the history of content and methodological development of engineer training in Hungary. In Nagyn, B. V., Murphy, M., Järvinen, H.-M., & Kálmán, A. (Eds.), *Varietas delectat... Complexity is the new normality. SEFI 47th Annual Conference* (pp. 795-804). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Budapest, Hungary. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14656551.

From Drawings to Digital Devices - Additives to the History of Content and Methodological Development of Engineer Training in Hungary

György Molnár
associate professor
Budapest, Hungary

Beáta Orosz
PhD student
Budapest, Hungary

Zoltán Szűts
associate professor
Budapest, Hungary

Conference Key Areas: Diversity in Engineering Education, Diversity in Engineering Education?

Keywords: Engineer Training, STEM, Drawings, ICT

ABSTRACT

In the past, teachers have been drawing on the blackboard, but today they are using digital devices that allow for the precision needed in the engineering industry. On the one hand, this significant change is generated by the rapidly changing technology; on the other hand, there is an increasing expectation from our society. The history of engineering training is also influenced by the aforementioned trends and their impact. In this development, the role of the so-called STEM is important, the application of science, information technologies, engineering knowledge, skills in the world of work. There is a growing need for businesses to adjust, and training systems, such as engineering training, should be prepared according to market orientated expectations. Progress can only be achieved if teachers, in addition to the students, keep pace with the rapid changes and effectively adapt the possibilities of digitalization to the teaching process. One of the lines of the new labour market competences is the demands of companies on robotics and the existence of programming skills, which are specially developed in mentor programs that require interdisciplinary collaboration. These methods provide a new approach and ready-made solutions to the entrepreneurial sphere.

At Budapest University of Technology and Education the implementing of WEDO 2.0, LEGO Mindstorm EV3 Education program, myDAQ or the World Robot Olympiad tournaments, we are able to provide the new kind of support that the world of work today requires of new graduates.

PREFACE

Digital competencies in today's world of digitalization are becoming more and more appreciated. This can be accompanied by a closer and more progressive attachment to the processing of some specific subject content. Such is e.g. teaching the fundamentals of programming and information technology in higher education, as

acquiring this knowledge is important for all engineering disciplines. In our presentation, we discuss these issues, which we wish to support with our experience in higher education.

The purpose of our presentation is to explore the ways subject matter and curricular developments coupled with innovative methodological solutions in the 21st century contributed to the evolution of engineer training as it is today. The connection between modern education and industry and the engineer with convertible skills are essential to industry. It has been proven that industrial success is based on the development of engineering training as well.

While our goal is not to provide a detailed history of our university, we would like to point to a few landmarks. The establishment of this institution balancing contemporary external and internal demands coincided with the accelerating industrial development made possible at first by the Reform Age and later by the Compromise of 1867. As a result of the establishment of various factories capable of producing at European or international standards cooperation began between universities and manufacturers, giving rise to an early form of dual training schemes. József Stoczek, the first rector of the university invited the leading industrial developers and scientists including Donát Bánki, Károly Zipernovszky, and Vince Wartha to teach here. All of the abovementioned developments resulted in Hungary achieving a level of industrial growth and production rivalling that of Sweden after the Compromise, and during the long 19th century education became an answer to questions related to problems arising in the international economic and political sphere.

One effective response to these challenges was provided by training at the contemporary University of Technology. We often recommend our students to read the gazettes of the Association of Engineers and Architects published at the end of the 19th century to see that these outstanding men were not only excellent industrialists, but internationally acclaimed creative individuals.

At the same time, we are equally proud of the scholarly and technological achievements realized in the interwar area. but since then the world has changed tremendously and educational institutions and education itself are faced with the task of providing answers to the challenges of the 21st century.

We used these examples to show how the internationally acclaimed achievements of engineering training at the University of Technology in the 19th century live on today. Furthermore, let us offer some personal examples showing the connection between the industrial or business sphere and that of academia. Although trained as an electrical engineer, I became an engineer-instructor and my colleague after a career as an economist joined the university as an instructor of economics.

Our essay explores related examples substantiated by professional experiences and that of full time students enrolled in engineering programs.

1 THE EDUCATION SYSTEM

1.1 Education long ago and nowadays

In the past, teachers have been drawing on the blackboard. The students nowadays don't prefer this method, because in this situation the teacher stands back to the audience while writing onto the board, students cannot hear the explanation, and cannot see and read the epigraph and illustrations from the back of the classroom.

Due to technical development in the education it is possible to use more modern, spectacular and visualized methods. The ICT tools and the rapidly developing

technology increasingly change the everyday way of life and lifestyle, and increase the need for the digitalization of different parts of life [15]. One of these parts is the education itself, because of the stronger presence of technical achievements.

In engineering education, precision, accuracy are really as important, as visualization. Because of these, non-observance of technical achievements would be not only impossible, but a huge mistake, because consistent usage of ICT tools helps teachers, and also students. In higher education tendencies of Industry 4.0, digital microtrends and models seemed firmly established, for example Flipped Classroom, BYOD and BYOC theories, gamification, electronic learning places, and different phenomena of media convergence. Due to the effect of the ICT tools, digital culture spreads and goes ahead against traditional culture, informal learning became more important, new ways of learning, new learning environments emerged and the role of social media is valued as well.

1.2 The main characteristics and deficiencies of engineer training

"As the dean of a college of technology said once he had many times presented degrees to engineers, whom he did not consider as such real professionals despite their passing the respective examinations.. When he was asked to describe a real engineer he had emphasized the cultural and social responsibility. He also pointed out that people directing either a scientific research project or a manufacturing effort had not been prepared to fulfil such responsibilities. Furthermore, he argued that many managers had not been familiar with the latest management skills, thus there was a serious need for the emphasis on the human side in the given training programs." [5]. In *The human aspect of higher education pedagogy*. Attila Mészáros singles out several unfortunate phenomena currently impacting engineering training programs. These include the high value assigned to passivity in learning positions and that of the respective information in entrance application procedures along with the weakened judgment of the individual succumbing to the unilateral scholarly authority which was leading to the eventual omission of the human factor. The respective training programs are generating a strong conditioning impact and are characterised by unilateral professional specification. All these features tend to narrow one's perspective and negatively impact social skills and personal qualities [4].

Engineers have to face a number of challenges in the 21st century. Engineering professionals have to fulfil several roles, communicate in a variety of ways either with fellow engineers or non-professionals, while considering and reconciling a wide variety of interests. Although the education system should be able to prepare students for handling such situations, the development of social, communicational, and cooperation skills demand a higher number of subjects related to social functioning and pedagogy. The emphasis on subjects focusing on economics resulted in a lower priority on the humanities and social sciences whose integrated perspective is required for becoming familiar with the organisational know-how. The globalization of environmental problems including the worsening air pollution and the loss of green areas increases the importance of sustainable development-oriented training. Fortunately, several positive developments have taken place in the given institutions [2, 4, 16].

Life practice-oriented training providing information not determined by the trainers' perspective and qualification should be included in engineering education. In addition

to digitalization cooperation with business can offer a solution for these problems and deficiencies. [4]

1.3 Developing possibilities in engineers' education based on a session of CAETS and the sustainable developmental goals of UN

The main focus of engineers' education is adequacy for present-day needs. In 2013 there was a session of CAETS in Budapest. [6] This event was really significant, because of the participation of the 26 member countries all engineering academies. They all together accepted that recommendations, which are still valid nowadays. The expectation was to train engineers, who are able to initiate technical advancements, and contribute to general social wealth.

It can be efficient only if we as teachers incite engineering students for problem solving and teamwork, and if we incorporate the results of the latest researches and innovations into the training, and take advantage of technological possibilities. In case of cooperation of engineers from academic and industrial sphere, it is easier to realize integrated thinking, science and technology developing. Engineers' education has to adapt to present-days social challenges. One element of this is the existence of rapidly changing social and labour market needs. That is why training processes have to contain substances which prepare students not only for knowledge and specifications, but flexibility and adaptability for new needs and challenges, too.

All of these changes innervate lifelong learning, and the education of scientific and technological topics. In today's society, the other buzzword is sustainability, which includes individuals and communities' reformation, accommodation for economic, social and cultural environment and these continuous changes and transformation. Sustainability has serious educational implications and nexus, in connection with sustainable development goals of UN. [1, 6, 7, 8, 10, 11, 13]

Some part of it connects to engineers educations, these are the following [1]:

- “Equal access to affordable and high quality technical, professional and higher education (for example university) trainings for every man and woman to 2030.
- Increasing numbers of young and adults, who have the adequate technical and professional competencies for labour market needs, decent work and business entrepreneurial needs to 2030.
- Gender equality in education, and equal access for every level of education and training for everybody, included disadvantaged groups (handicapped, autochthon, vulnerable people) to 2030.
- Increasing number of available scholarships globally, which are aimed to help students from third world countries, developing islands and African countries. With these scholarships it is possible to study professions, ICT, technological, engineering and scientific subjects.
- Increasing numbers of highly qualified teachers and trainers, also in the developing countries, with teacher training cooperation to 2030.

- Green universities: new vocational subjects in connection with renewable energy.”

According to a survey of István Lükő [3], there is a reason for the lack of the environmental, sustainability perspective and curricula in the training programs of engineers. The explanation is that there always will be environmental engineers, who solve the problems and eliminate environmental damages, which was caused by non-environmental professionals. Fortunately, this approach started to disappear, nowadays more and more technological and economic faculty contains curricula in connection with sustainability.

In 2009 István Lükő made a comparative survey in this topic. Data are from Internet and his own syllabus research [3]. He aimed to examine the currently existing and newly created subjects, and these appellation, contents and weighting in curricula. The research concerned the following countries: Great-Britain 3, Austria 3, Turkey 1, Romania 2, China 2, Taiwan 2, Canada 2, Germany 3. The numbers show the observed universities in each country. Lükő examined 35 faculties, and evinced, that besides traditional academic and technological faculties, more universities are open to modern specializations, as an answer to the challenges of the XXI. century. As mentioned, engineers' education has to contain more social subjects, to prepare students for the difficulties of the labour market.

Which were the most frequent subject titles?

- Innovation management, Environmental management, Law (general, environment–related, engineering-related) Sustainability and environmental management,
- Classic social science subjects: Sociology Environmental Sociology, Psychology, Group management, Economics, Engineering Ethics, New disciplines and related special subjects and modules: Social anthropology, Social problems and social policies, Urban sociology, Stress analysis, Individual design and research effort, Human ecology, Globalization and development, Environmental entrepreneurship, Due to the widespread presence of computerization engineers have to cope with several social consequences. Consequently, the Information Society and Digital Culture program of the University of Kent focuses on the connection between the student, the information society, and digital culture.
- The most complex and possibly most comprehensive courses are offered by the Chaoyang University of Technology. The course offerings include
- Planning and Design of Civil Works in Urban Area, Field Safety and Environmental Protection, Government Procurement Law and Act for Promotion of Infrastructure Project, Human Resources Management. Completion of these subjects is worth 3 credits [3].

These subjects have been complemented with new type disciplines responding to options and challenges raised by digital pedagogy, information technology, and digital culture These concerns are expressed by the objectives of the Sustainable Development Framework System accepted by the UN in 2015. While the Framework System is based on balanced social development, long term economic growth and

environmental protection, the fourth pillar includes improving the quality of education. Hungary has played an important role in the elaboration and shaping of the Framework System from its inception. The chart below shows the 17 objectives of the Framework System.

Fig 1. Sustainable Development Goals [14]

2. ENGINEER TRAINING WITH SPECIAL EMPHASIS ON STEM PROGRAMS

The latest Vocational Training 4.0 strategy reiterates that the Hungarian economic sphere needs engineers, and experts with informatics and natural science background. Graduates with MTMI skills can be prepared to achieve success in the labour market via STEM oriented skill development programs delivered by enterprises. Such training programs and the latest vocational training-related initiatives aim to achieve a 40% rate in the enrolment in such programs among students applying to higher education. In recent years significant developments took place as while in 2012 only 22% applied to such programs, said figure reached 29% in 2018. The given enrolment rate can be increased by short-term, job-related competence development programs focusing on mathematics, informatics, and natural science-related skills.

Current examples include the professional and business-related training programs developed by the National Instruments Hungary Ltd coupled with vocational competitions. The training programs focus on students enrolled in electric engineering and engineer informatics training and provide specialized training with a specialized methodology for those at career entry positions or engineering candidates. The regular competition opportunities include the LEGO Robot contests and the LEGO Robot programming camps in the summer. Furthermore, the company offers an NI Mentor program aiming at popularizing natural sciences and promoting the algorithmic perspective required for the engineering profession at an early age. Accordingly, specially designed devices and the tools of LEGO Education provide a sense of accomplishment. Students using these devices developed for educational purposes and graphic programming options not only prepare for a career in engineering, but by solving tasks appropriate for their age they actually perform real engineering tasks while still at school. The program utilizes a state of the art and attractive set of devices as students in the lower segment of elementary school can work with the LEGO WeDo 2.0 in solving exciting tasks and students in the higher section of elementary school can become familiar with simple and more complex movements via the LEGO Mindstorms EV3. They can achieve a sense of success via solving automation-related exercises. Secondary school students can work with

more complex problems by the help of the LabVIEW, and their knowledge of physics and electronics can help in solving problems via the myDAQ. The main levels of the mentor program and its grade-based distribution is described by the figure below.

Fig 2. Vocational Training 4.0 strategy

3. EMPIRICAL RESEARCH PERFORMED AMONG ENGINEERING STUDENTS

Empirical research focuses on the digital competence skill level and device use of young engineering candidate students along with the impact of applied ICT methods. Said survey was performed in autumn 2017 via a quantitative questionnaire with a layered sample of 100. The sample population included full time engineering students enrolled in a special career preparatory course titled "I will be an engineer!" The sample that eventually served as a basis for the research included 94 respondents. The explorations were performed by an interactive, experience-based kahoot type measuring device. Our survey took advantage of the Bring Your Own Device method and used close ended questions in order to obtain data to be processed via a descriptive statistical approach. The respective results were displayed in diagrams and we deployed a multivariable statistical method, the Kruskal-Wallis analysis. Keeping spatial restrictions in mind, we have compiled a brief summary of the most significant and characteristic results by descriptive statistical methods.

The next figure shows that 91% of the engineering students participating in the survey graduated from high school but did not obtain a vocational qualification. Only 6% of the respondents graduated from a vocational secondary school with a maturation certificate or a high school diploma and a vocational qualification as well. Another 3% came from a special vocational high school after earning a vocational qualification.

Fig 3. Distribution of the educational qualification of the respondents Source: author’s own chart

The next figure reveals the level of the respondents’ openness to the modern and new open teaching and learning methods. It can be concluded that 50% of the respondents are fully open to new educational methods (4), 28%, that is over a quarter, are significantly open (3) and 12% (2) and 10% (1) indicated that they were reluctant toward new generation learning methods respectively.

Fig 4. Distribution of the levels of students’ openness toward modern, new generation learning methods, source author’s own chart

4. SUMMARY

Current learning theory models emphasize the need for the inclusion of on-line digital devices and educational material content in order to provide a background for modern and effective teaching. Educational materials have been expanded to include

new media elements, videos, animations, and e-books. Such developments and trends can be beneficial for assuring the quality of engineering training as well. The digital world and its devices increasingly support the improvement of STEM-related skills. Most of the abovementioned developments focus on meeting the demands of the labour market while shaping the respective competences of engineering students in an informal way. It was also proven that today's engineering students are open toward new methodological cultures and the application of pedagogical approaches promoting a shared, cooperative competitive perspective. Such tendencies coincide with the aspirations of the current Industry 4.0 and the Vocational training 4.0 strategies as well. Digital technology and digital culture are expected to be represented by separate subjects as shown by the draft version of the National Curriculum issued in 2018. The high priority assigned to these areas can facilitate the formation and development of the digital competence section of engineer training in higher education institutions. Consequently, engineering students can obtain knowledge, experiences, and skills required for the completion of such programs.

5. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research project of the MTA-BME Open Content Development Research Group is funded by the Content Pedagogy Research Program of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences.

REFERENCES

- [1] István, Lükő (2017), Oktatás és fenntarthatóság az ENSZ Fenntartható Fejlődési Célok (SDG 2016-2030) rendszere alapján, *EDU*, Vol. 7, No. 3, pp 7-31.
- [2] István, Lükő (2015), Mérnökképzés, szakképzés és a társadalomtudományok a 21. században, *EDU: szakképzés- és környezetpedagógia elektronikus szakfolyóirat*, Vol. 5, No. 1, pp. 45-62.
- [3] István, Lükő (2009), Összehasonlító vizsgálat az egyetemek társadalomtudományi tárgyainak oktatásáról Kézirat, Sopron, pp. 56
- [4] Attila, Mészáros (2016), A felsőoktatás-pedagógia humanisztikus aspektusai, Tanulás és fejlődés, Karlovitz János Tibor, Stúrovo, pp 63.
- [5] Coenraad, van Houten (1999), *Erwachsenenbildung als Willenserweckung Freies Geistesleben*. London: Temple Lodge Publishing.
- [6] <http://www.mszt.hu/web/guest/mernokakademiak>, downloaded: 25.04.2019.

-
- [7] BIBB (2004), Umweltbildung für nachhaltige Entwicklung in der beruflichen Aus- und Weiterbildung
- [8] Carl Lindberg (2009), Education for Sustainable Development – a necessity for shaping the future LLinE Vol. 14, No.1
- [9] György, Molnár (2011), Új módszerek a pedagógiai gyakorlatban - az IKT alapú megoldások tükrében. *Szakképzési Szemle* Vol. 27, No. 3, pp. 170-177.
- [10] János, Farkas- Tamás, Dénes (2015), A humán társadalom elmélete. Gondolat Kiadó, Budapest
- [11] OFI (2012): A fenntartható fejlődés szempontjai a felsőoktatási minőségirányítás intézményi gyakorlatában OFI, Budapest
- [12] Tibor, Faragó (2013), A nemzetközi fejlesztési együttműködés céljai és a fenntartható fejlődési célok. *Statisztikai Szemle*, Vol. 91, No. 8-9, pp.823-841.
- [13] Tibor, Faragó (2015), A fenntartható fejlődés új ENSZ programja Tanulmány, Budapest
- [14] <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/?menu=1300>, downloaded: 29.04.2019.
- [15] András, Benedek (2013), Paths and Traps in the Forest of the Digitalization of Education, In: Benedek, András; Nyíri, Kristóf (szerk.) *How to Do Things with Pictures : Skill, Practice, Performance*, Peter Lang Internationaler Verlag der Wissenschaften, pp. 11-19., 9 p.
- [16] Beetham, Helen, and Rhona Sharpe (2019), *Rethinking Pedagogy for a Digital Age: Principles and Practices of Design*. Routledge; 3 edition (June 25, 2019) ISBN-10: 0815369255